

ECO-CORE AND ITS PERFORMANCE IN SANDWICH STRUCTURAL APPLICATION

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SUMMARY

Eco-Core is a fire resistant structural core material for composite sandwich structures. Structural performance of Eco-Core glass/vinyl ester sandwich beams was evaluated for transverse and edgewise loadings. Core shear, core tension and face sheet microbuckling were the failure modes and they can be predicted by the existing analytical models.

Keywords: Sandwich structure, structural performance, Eco-Core, fire resistant, failure

INTRODUCTION

Fire has been a major problem for both mobile (mass transit and marine) and immobile (buildings and civil infrastructure) structures. With the wide use of polymer composites in structural applications, potential for fire hazards has increased. Norwegian composite minesweeper fire [1] demonstrated the vulnerability of composite ships against fire. September 11, 2001 twin tower fire and collapse have demonstrated the vulnerability of our unprotected steel skyscrapers. Although fire cannot be completely eliminated, it can be mitigated to reduce the loss of life and property. Extensive research is being conducted to improve fire safety of composite materials for various applications. Some of these results are summarized by Sorathia and Perez [2] for naval applications. Shivakumar and his co-researchers [3-5] have proposed a method of fire mitigation through blocking/containing the fire by using a fire resistant core material in sandwich structures. They developed a material called Eco-Core from a waste product from coal burnt thermal power plants and high char binder.

It is well known that sandwich structures are highly efficient in carrying flexural loads. Sandwich structures with composite face sheet and PVC or balsa core materials are widely used in marine applications. US and European navies are using or considering to use composite sandwich for building mine sweepers, coastal protection ships, destroyers, etc. In fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) 50% weight is resin and its char yield is less than 15%, resulting in 43% weight of volatiles released in the case of fire, which makes it highly susceptible to fire. Like resin, PVC cores offer no resistance to fire. On the other hand balsa tolerates or inhibits the growth of fire but it suffers from non-uniform density (depends on the source and life time seasonal variation), large moisture ingress and rotting. Recent studies [6] have shown that about 800% density change

and 35% volume change in balsa are expected when exposed to sea water, which makes it susceptible for self destruction. The novelty of the Eco-Core [3-5] is that it uses little binder (high char yield content) and large volume of ceramic hollow microbubbles (Cenosphere) together press molded to required size and shape. The Eco-Core has superior mechanical properties, excellent fire resistant properties (passed Mil Spec 2031 up to 75 kW/m²) and is non toxic [3-5]. The focus of this research is a test evaluation of structural performance of Eco-Core sandwich panel and its comparison with the predictive models presented in reference 7. This paper discusses design of test specimens for various types of failure, namely, shear, flexure and edgewise compression; verification of the design by experiments and identification of failure modes.

NOMENCLATURE AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Sandwich beam consists of a lightweight core material which is covered by face sheets on both sides. Figure 1 is the schematic of the sandwich beam cross section. The nomenclature used in the design of test specimens is defined: t_c is the core thickness, t_f is the face sheet thickness and d is the sandwich thickness which is the distance between two centroids of the face sheets ($d=t_c+t_f$). The width of the panel is represented by b . Compression strength, elastic modulus, shear strength and shear modulus of the core are σ_c , E_c , τ_c and G_c , respectively. Strength and elastic modulus of the face sheet are σ_f and E_f , respectively. The nomenclature used is the same as in the standard text books on sandwich structure [8, 9].

The face sheet considered is FGI 1854 glass/Derakane 510A-40 vinyl ester composite and the core material is Eco-Core with a nominal density of 0.5 g/cc. Table 1 lists the mechanical properties of the face sheet [10] and the core material [3].

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the sandwich cross section and nomenclature.

The test specimens are designed to simulate typical failures of core shear, face yielding, face wrinkling, shear buckling, face microbuckling and general buckling that occur in sandwich panels as in references 8 and 9. These failures can be simulated by short beam shear, flexure (4-point bend), and edgewise compression tests. Test specimens were designed using the material properties listed in Table 1 and equations given in reference 7.

Table 1 Material properties of face sheet and core materials.

Material	Tensile		Compressive		Shear	
	Modulus GPa	Strength MPa	Modulus GPa	Strength MPa	Modulus GPa	Strength MPa
Face sheet	29.2	512.5	31.9	363.4	4.0	77.1
Eco-Core	2.54	6.46	1.14	21.85	0.97	4.61

FAILURE LOAD EXPRESSIONS FOR DIFFERENT TEST CONDITIONS

Relevant equations to predict failure loads for the three different tests and various failure conditions are summarized here and are used to compare with the experiment. All these equations are taken from reference 7.

Short Beam Shear Test Specimen

The short beam shear test was designed to measure shear strength of the core material. Four-point and 3-point bend loaded testing are commonly used. Here we chose 4-point bend with quarter point loading. Figure 2 shows the schematic of the short beam shear test. L is the specimen length, S is the span of the support and $S/2$ is the load span. The typical failure mode in short beam shear test is core shear, a 45° cracking starting from the mid-thickness as illustrated in Fig. 2. Critical load at failure P_f can be related to core shear strength and test specimen geometry and the equation is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 Short beam shear test configuration, failure mode and failure load equation.

Four-Point Flexure Test Specimen

Figure 3(a) shows the schematic of 4-point flexure test with third point loading. Under the flexure loading, sandwich beams are observed to fail by three modes, namely, face yielding, core shear and face wrinkling depending on span to depth ratio and face sheet-

core thickness ratio, and properties of face sheet and core material. Figure 3(b) illustrates the potential failure modes and the failure loads that can be calculated from specimen geometry and material properties (Equations 2-4).

Figure 3 Four-point flexure test configuration and potential failure modes.

Edgewise Compression Test Specimen

The test specimen and the possible failure modes under edgewise compression are shown in Fig. 4. The failure modes are general buckling, shear buckling, face sheet microbuckling (which is the same as face sheet yielding), face wrinkling and face dimpling. The associated failure loads for all the cases are summarized in Fig. 4.

Based on Equations 1 through 9, failure loads can be calculated for different specimen geometry and material properties. Design plots of failure load vs. specimen length and the comparison with test results are presented in Testing, Results and Discussion section.

Figure 4 Edgewise compression test configuration and possible failure modes.

FABRICATION OF SANDWICH PANEL AND SPECIMEN

The sandwich face sheets were unidirectional 3-ply FGI 1854 glass/Derakane 510A-40 vinyl ester composite fabricated by Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Media (VARTM) process as explained in reference 13. The thickness of the face sheet achieved was 1.4 mm. Eco-Core panel was adhesively bonded to the face sheets. The adhesive used was Loctite Hysol E-90FL epoxy adhesive. It is a toughened and medium viscosity adhesive with tensile strength of 13 MPa, lap shear strength of 5.6 MPa and elongation of 64%. Vacuum bag was used for bonding and the pressure applied was 20 inHg (0.068 MPa). The sandwich panel was kept in vacuum bag at room temperature for 8 hours for curing of the adhesive.

TESTING, RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

Short beam shear, 4-point flexure and edgewise compression tests were conducted on sandwich specimens made of FGI 1854 glass/Derakane 510A-40 face sheet and Eco-Core. The thicknesses of the face sheet and the Eco-Core were 1.4 mm and 25.4 mm, respectively. The tests were conducted in an Instron 4202 testing machine with a 10 kip load cell. During the tests, load and displacement were recorded continuously by data acquisition system and the failures of the specimens were monitored visually, by digital camcorder, and a high speed photography for some cases.

Short Beam Shear Test

The short beam shear test was conducted in accordance with ASTM standard C393-00. The specimen length was 152 mm and width was 51 mm. Quarter point loading was applied. The supporting span length was 102 mm and the upper loading span was 61 mm. The specimens were loaded at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The test was repeated for three specimens.

Eco-Core sandwich specimens showed brittle fracture at failure. Based on Eq. 1, predicted shear failure load is 12,689 N while the experimental average failure load is 12,064 N with a standard deviation of 916 N. The prediction is about 5% larger than the test data. This difference is within the experimental scatter that is expected for these materials.

Figure 5 illustrates the failure mode of Eco-Core sandwich specimens. The Eco-Core specimens demonstrated typical shear failure showing a 45° crack in the core, between the top load point and the bottom support at one end. This was followed by immediate crack at the other end.

Figure 5 Shear failure modes of Eco-Core sandwich beam.

Four-Point Flexure Test

The 4-point flexure test was conducted in accordance with ASTM standard C393-00. The specimen width was 51 mm. Third point loading was applied. The specimens were tested for five different span (S) lengths, namely, 127mm, 191mm, 254mm, 394mm and 508mm. The specimens were loaded at a cross-head speed of 1.27 mm/min and the

load-displacement was continuously recorded. The test was repeated for three specimens.

None of the specimens failed by the possible modes shown in Fig. 3. The failure was initiated by vertical cracks at the bottom of the core within the two upper loading points as core tension failure (see Fig. 6(a)). Fig. 6(b) shows the ultimate failure which is the shear crack followed by face sheet-core separation. Core tension failure was not reported, heretofore, as a failure mode in sandwich panels. Because the Eco-Core is relatively brittle and is stronger in compression than in tension the core tension failure occurred.

Figure 6 Crack initiation, propagation and ultimate failure of Eco-Core sandwich panel under 4-pt flexure loading.

The core tension failure load can be derived using the beam theory and is given by:

$$P_f = \frac{12D\sigma_{ct}b}{St_c E_{ct}} \quad (10)$$

where σ_{ct} and E_{ct} are the tensile strength and modulus, respectively, of the core material. Predicted failure loads versus span/depth ratio for all possible failure modes are plotted in Fig. 7 along with the experimental data. The test data agrees very well with the predicted core tension failure loads. Therefore, core tension is the major failure mode for Eco-Core or brittle core sandwich composite panels. The failure is tensile for $S/d > 4$ and is core shear for $S/d \leq 4$.

Edgewise Compression Test

Edgewise compression test was conducted in accordance with ASTM standard C364-00. The specimen ends were supported by two lateral support clamps made of rectangular steel bars fastened together to prevent the specimen from slipping from the fixture. The two ends of the specimens were machined to be flat and parallel to each other and perpendicular to the loading. The test was performed at the cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The specimens were tested for six different unsupported specimen

lengths (L) resulting in length/depth (L/d) ratios of 5, 7, 11, 13, 18 and 20. 25.4 mm thick core was used for L/d ratios of 5 and 7 while 12.7mm thick core was used to simulate long L/d ratios of 11, 13, 18 and 20.

Figure 7 Comparison of experiment and theory for 4-pt flexure loaded Eco-Core sandwich beam.

The predicted and experimental failure loads are plotted versus specimen length/depth (L/d) ratio in Fig. 8. The symbols represent the experimental data while the lines represent the predicted values. The experimental failure loads (P_f/b) for L/d of 5, 7 and 11 were 980, 1,129, and 912N/mm, respectively. These results agreed well with the predicted face sheet compressive microbuckling failure load (1,015 N/mm) from Eq. 7. The face sheet micorbuckling failure is shown in Figs. 9(a). For $L/d=5$, initial and ultimate failures were clearly due to compressive microbuckling of face sheet whereas for $L/d=7$ and 11, the failure was a combination of face sheet microbuckling, face sheet-core separation/debonding and buckling (See Fig. 9(b)). For $L/d=13$, 18 and 20, failures were a mixture of sandwich general buckling and face sheet separation. One specimen each of $L/d=18$ and 20 showed clearly general buckling of the sandwich column (See Fig. 9(c)). Based on the test results one can conclude that for $L/d < 7$ the failure is by face sheet microbuckling, for $7 \leq L/d \leq 13$ the failure is combination of face sheet microbuckling, debonding and buckling, and for $L/d > 13$ the failure is by general buckling.

Figure 8 Comparison of experiment and theory for edgewise compression loaded Eco-Core sandwich column.

Figure 9 Edgewise compression failure modes of Eco-Core sandwich specimens.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Eco-Core, a fire resistant core material for sandwich composite structures developed under the US Navy (ONR) program, was used to study its performance as a sandwich beam with glass/vinyl ester face sheet. Test specimens were designed to simulate shear, flexural, and edgewise compression loadings. Failure loads and modes were compared with each other and the analytical predictions. In the case of transversely loaded (4-point) beams Eco-Core sandwich specimens failed by core shear for span/depth (S/d) ≤ 4

and the failure mode changed to core tension for $S/d > 4$. This is attributed to weak tensile strength of the core material. An expression for core tension failure load, based on beam theory, is given by $P_f = \frac{12D\sigma_{ct}b}{St_c E_{ct}}$. Under edgewise compression, face sheet microbuckling and general buckling are the two potential failure modes for Eco-Core sandwich composites. For specimen length/depth ratio $L/d < 7$ the failure is by face sheet microbuckling, for $7 \leq L/d \leq 13$ the failure is combination of face sheet microbuckling, debonding and buckling, and for $L/d > 13$ the failure is by general buckling. Predictions from the existing equations agreed well with the experiment.

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